

The Geopolitics of Economic Coercion: Mapping US Unilateral Coercive Measures (2020-2026) and its influence over the BRICS+ Regulatory Agenda

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Abstract

Since the end of the Second World War, the U.S. dollar has consolidated its position as the main currency of international trade and as a central instrument of power within the International Monetary and Financial System. In this context, debates on de-dollarization have emerged among BRICS countries as an attempt to reduce dependence on the dollar and challenge the power structure historically shaped by the United States. Thus, this article analyzes the influence of Chinese foreign policy on the BRICS+ de-dollarization agenda, focusing on the role of the internationalization of the renminbi. The study seeks to answer the following research question: how does the internationalization of the renminbi, as an instrument of Chinese foreign policy, influence the debate and initiatives of de-dollarization within BRICS? To address this question, the research adopts a qualitative approach based on a critical perspective of International Political Economy and the power relations that structure the International Monetary System, using a deductive method. The findings indicate that although BRICS members share a common political interest in reducing dependence on the U.S. dollar, the de-dollarization process reflects internal disputes and different national interests. In this context, China emerges as a central actor in shaping the debate by promoting the internationalization of the renminbi and encouraging its use in intra-bloc trade. Through strategies such as the creation of alternative payment systems, the strengthening of economic partnerships with the Global South, and the expansion of BRICS+, China seeks to expand its monetary influence.

Keywords: BRICS; Unilateral Coercive Measures; Geoprocessing.

Introduction

The current global order is transitioning from a period of neoliberal integration to one of profound geoeconomic fragmentation. In this landscape, the distinction between unilateral coercive measures (UCMs), protectionist policies and national defense strategies has become increasingly blurred (Brancaccio; Califano, 2023). This shift characterizes contemporary geoeconomics as the strategic use of economic instruments to produce beneficial geopolitical results through the containment of systemic rivals (Wigell, 2016).

Historically, the post-World War II international economic order was structured around multilateral institutions created to establish a liberal capitalism paradigm, which systemically benefited the countries with the wealthiest economies and the greatest corporations in detriment of less developed countries with less competitive corporations. Thus, it was carefully designed to preserve asymmetrical power dynamics (Mounssif, 2025) throughout transnational markets. Within this context, UCMs represent a unilateral exercise of power that bypasses the United Nations-led multilateral framework, in what regards general international law principles and specific rules on trade, investments, currency, corporate rights, government obligations etc., directly challenging the principle of sovereign equality and non-intervention in internal affairs of other states. The UN is the network that articulates several other networks. For example: IMF, WTO, World Bank, Swift are part of the UN System, even if they are not formally part of the UN Organization. They are more like “cousins”, than “daughters”. UCM can be appraised as illicit through the perspective of UN law, WTO law, IMF law, International Customary law, etc. While the economic and legal implications of these sanctions are widely debated in International Relations literature review, in broad, generic terms, their specific spatial distribution and territorial footprint have received limited attention from a geoeconomic and cartographic perspective.

This study addresses this research gap by mapping the expansion of US sanctions from 2020 to 2026. The primary research question investigates how the spatial concentration of U.S. UCMs has evolved during the recent systemic decoupling and how this geographical pressure drives the BRICS+ bloc towards a regulatory agenda (Vasconcelos, 2018), that can strengthen the objective conditions for its members to uphold their national Sovereignty. and how this geographical pressure drives the BRICS+ bloc towards a sovereign regulatory agenda (Vasconcelos, 2018).

This article adds a necessary cartographic dimension to the debate on global governance. It argues that the mapping of UCMs reveals a "Geography of Punishment" that paradoxically accelerates the consolidation of the BRICS+ as an alternative pole of power, pushing the bloc to develop independent economic structures with interconnected canals to safeguard its territorial and economic autonomy.

Methodology

This research employs a quantitative and geospatial approach to examine the spatial distribution and intensity of U.S. UCMs applied between 2020 and 2026. The methodology is designed to be replicable, allowing for the territorial mapping of economic pressure across different jurisdictions. This approach offers a scalable model for academic researchers, geopolitical analysts, and international monitoring bodies to systematically track the spatial footprint of unilateral coercive measures, thereby facilitating a more granular understanding of geoeconomic fragmentation.

In order to avoid the postmodernist subjectivity of individual theoretical frameworks, we decide to initiate a long-term research program from the most objective, authoritative and available source of information. This methodological option at this moment is due only to a pragmatical decision considering the extremely short deadline for the submission of this paper. However, this decision should not be interpreted as an absolute choice of a definitive source. This is just a way to experiment the geoprocessing methodology to make the best use of the available data. In other words, this paper is more about the broad methodological possibilities than the specific finding of this first application of such methodology. The primary data was retrieved from the U.S. Department of the Treasury's Office of Foreign Assets Control (OFAC), specifically utilizing the consolidated datasets provided by the Sanctions Explorer (C4ADS, 2026). The temporal scope covers the period from January 2020 to March 2026. This timeframe was selected to encompass the systemic shift in U.S. geoeconomic strategy, characterized by the transition from targeted individual designations to broad sectoral blockades following the 2022 escalation in Eastern Europe, and the response of the Global South, specifically the 2024 expansion of the BRICS bloc.

The research regarding UCMs undertaken in this research adopted the conceptual framework established by the United Nations Special Rapporteur on the Negative Impact of Unilateral Coercive Measures. (United Nations, 2020). However, the UN-UCM analytical framework embraces a broader scope of measures than the ones we had access to through the US OFAC database. Accordingly, it is important to clarify that our understanding about the diversified nature of instruments to impose UCM far exceed those contemplated by the US-OFAC database. This research only worked within this sample of UCM because those were objectively available to be promptly used in the application of our geoprocessing methodological procedures. But, OFAC is not responsible for UCMs related, for example to: WTO regulations regarding use of tariffs; Access to SWIFT exchange channels; Diplomatic extortion; Inside-trade market manipulation; Violations of International Law Principles; Violation of UN law; International Humanitarian Law; etc. Anyway, the US-UCM exposed in the OFAC database also includes information regarding measures against individuals, organizations, vessels, and aircraft. This allowed an analysis based on their territorial and systemic impact. Considering the technical analysis and description of economic coercive mechanisms documented in the UN-UCM analytical framework, organized by Alena F. Douhan (DOUHAN, 2020; 2022), we adapted a simpler typology consistent of four broad categories:

- Financial Sanctions: Measures targeting liquidity, asset freezing, and restrictions on

- banking access (e.g., programs like IFSR and VENEZUELA-EO13850).
- Trade/General Sanctions: Traditional trade embargoes and restrictions on the movement of specific goods, including individual designations (e.g., Global Magnitsky).
- Sectoral Sanctions: Targeted measures against strategic economic pillars such as energy, defense, and technology (e.g., RUSSIA-EO14024 and CMIC).
- Secondary/Extraterritorial Sanctions: Measures targeting third-party actors who engage in business with sanctioned entities (e.g., SDGT and CAATSA).

Data processing was conducted using the R programming language. The raw spreadsheet of US sanctions was organized, categorized, and spatially linked to a digital world map. The methodology is divided into two main analytical visual outputs. First, a quantitative chart was developed to illustrate the volume of sanctions categorized by target sectors. Second, a choropleth map was generated via ggplot2 to visualize the geographical footprint and concentration of sanctions, quantifying "Sanction Intensity" (defined as the total number of designated entities per jurisdiction) [1].

Results

The quantitative mapping reveals a clear geographical bias in the application of U.S. coercive power. Based on the OFAC dataset (2020-2026), the total number of designated entities shows a highly concentrated distribution.

Figure 1 - Intensity of US Unilateral Coercive Measures (2020-2026).

Source: Prepared by the author based on U.S. Department of the Treasury (OFAC) data (2026).

As illustrated in the generated data (Figure 1), the Russian Federation is the primary target of OFAC UCMs, with over 1,800 designated entities. Within the Russian context, Sectoral Sanctions represent the overwhelming majority of designations.

[1] If you are interested in a more technical explanation about the geoprocessing methodology for some collaborative research on this topic, please contact me. I would appreciate the opportunity to apply this know-how in other BRICS related themes.

In contrast, data regarding Iran and Venezuela shows a predominance of Financial Sanctions. Furthermore, the data reveals a high volume of Secondary Sanctions categorized under Global/Thematic programs, which are not tied to a single sovereign territory but are applied transnationally.

Figure 2 – The Geography of Punishment: Spatial Distribution of US UCMs by Category (2020-2026)

Source: Prepared by the author based on U.S. Department of the Treasury (OFAC) data (2026).

The spatial distribution of these measures is visualized in the thematic map (Figure 2). The choropleth map illustrates a concentration of high-intensity sanctions in the Eurasian Axis and specific nodes of the Middle East.

When cross-referencing the spatial data with BRICS+ membership status, a stark disparity is observed within the bloc. The Russian Federation and Iran (a member as of 2024) are subjected to "Systemic" and "High-intensity" UCMs. China presents a different profile, with a lower absolute number of sanctioned entities compared to Russia, heavily concentrated in the Trade/General and specific Sectoral categories (such as the Chinese Military-Industrial Complex - CMIC). Meanwhile, other BRICS+ members, including Brazil, India, and the United Arab Emirates, appear as grey areas on the map, remaining largely unaffected by direct, massive OFAC designations, though they register isolated occurrences of secondary or thematic sanctions targeting specific individuals or commercial agents.

Finally, the temporal metadata from the 2020-2026 period indicates an acceleration in the update rate of the OFAC sanctions lists, with the inclusion of new entities occurring on a near-weekly basis across the mapped territories.

Discussion

The results confirm that UCMs have evolved into a central pillar of U.S. national security policy, functioning as an offensive geoeconomic strategy that creates a fragmented global space. By moving beyond the raw data presented in the results, the spatial vacuum and the concentrations on the map can be interpreted as the boundaries of the integrated global economy versus the territories being forcibly decoupled from it.

The disparity between Sectoral and Financial sanctions exposes distinct strategies of territorial encirclement. The massive sectoral attack on Russia aims to paralyze industrial and energy infrastructure, while the financial sanctions on Iran represent a liquidity strangulation strategy, disconnecting the territory from international banking clearing circuits. Furthermore, China's position in the mapping indicates a strategy of surgical selectivity. By targeting specific regulatory nodes (e.g., semiconductor firms), the U.S. seeks to isolate advanced segments of Chinese industry without triggering a total collapse of global supply chains.

However, as Brancaccio and Califano (2023) suggest, this strategy of exclusion assumes a unipolar world that no longer exists. The "Geography of Punishment", mapped in this study, acts as a direct catalyst for the BRICS+ Regulatory Agenda (Vasconcelos, 2018). The internal diversity of the sanctions' impact, ranging from total blockades on Russia to targeted extraterritorial threats against Chinese or Brazilian commercial agents, demonstrates that the bloc's search for institutional alternatives is a collective effort to build a multidimensional legal shield.

This spatial pressure explains the recent and urgent shifts in BRICS+ policy. The weaponization of the dollar and the SWIFT system have established the conditions of possibility for a systemic reconfiguration. As noted by Mohamed (2025), the trend towards de-dollarization within BRICS+ is a direct response to the vulnerabilities exposed by these sanctions, driving the bloc to develop alternative payment mechanisms to ensure financial sovereignty.

The cartographic omnipresence of Secondary and Thematic sanctions reveals the deterritorialization of punishment. U.S. jurisdiction pursues financial flows anywhere in the global space, eroding the sovereign right to trade of non-sanctioned countries like Brazil or India. To counter this creeping extraterritoriality, the BRICS+ agenda is moving from political rhetoric to technical implementation. Recent policy recommendations from the Brazilian presidency of the BRICS Think Tanks Council (BTTC) explicitly call for the creation of a "BRICS Clear" system, an independent cross-border settlement and depository infrastructure, and the strengthening of the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA) using local currencies (IPEA, 2025).

Geographically, the implementation of systems like BRICS Pay and the use of local currencies

represent an effort of re-territorialization of financial control. By creating a parallel geography of trade, the BRICS+ members are effectively shrinking the areas of vulnerability mapped in this study and expanding a zone of regulatory autonomy.

A limitation of this study is its exclusive reliance on OFAC data, which maps U.S. sanctions but does not capture the overcompliance of secondary markets, nor does it include European Union sanctions. Future studies should investigate the actual implementation and transaction volumes of the proposed BRICS+ financial mechanisms (such as the NDB's local currency loans) to measure how effectively they mitigate the spatial exclusion mapped in this research.

Conclusion

The United States' 2025 National Security Strategy explicitly proclaims its principles and priorities to maintain its "preeminence" over the world. The narrative of a zero-sum understanding of international relations attempts to justify a confrontational foreign policy to unambiguously impose its full spectrum dominance agenda upon friends and foes. This dichotomously fallacious mindset tends to treat alternative diplomatic initiatives as a geopolitical threat to its "core national interests". Accordingly, the recent U.S. administration increased exponentially its use of illicit Unilateral Coercive Measures against Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa.

Although each country is targeted individually as a tactic to maximize the asymmetry in the correlation of powers, the spatial mapping conducted in this study makes it evident that the ultimate goal is to attack the BRICS project itself. The bloc is targeted not only for the networks of international governance it has already created, but also for the alternate socioeconomical possibilities it presents for the global majority as a whole. Therefore, if these countries are actually being attacked for being part of a group, then it makes sense for them to conceive their defensive strategies, also, as a group.

The 2025 BRICS Leaders Declaration explicitly condemned the imposition of unilateral coercive measures and reaffirmed that BRICS member states do not impose or support non-UN Security Council authorized sanctions. The United Nations also acknowledges the gravity of this problem for a decade. It even proclaimed an annual "International Day against Unilateral Coercive Measures", as part of global efforts to raise awareness about their unlawfulness and negative impact. However, considering the US' manifest disregard for international law, BRICS+ should not underestimate the risks, incentives, and transaction costs of not approaching this threat through a cohesive, bloc-wide regulatory framework.

The mapping of U.S. UCMs between 2020 and 2026 reveals an economic landscape defined by geopolitically selective territorial exclusion. The escalation of sectoral and financial sanctions has effectively bifurcated the global economic space, creating a clear distinction between the integrated West and the coerced Global South. Yet, this study concludes that UCMs are inadvertently accelerating the transition toward a multipolar regulatory order.

By attempting to isolate strategic rivals through extraterritorial jurisdiction, the U.S. is fostering the consolidation of the BRICS+ as a necessary institutional alternative.

The maps generated in this research do show not only where sanctions are applied, but also, they highlight the pressure points that are serving as the birthplaces of a new international legality. As the BRICS+ expands its regulatory agenda, which is evidenced by the push for local currency trade, the strengthening of the NDB, and the proposed BRICS Clear infrastructure, the effectiveness of UCMs as a tool of hegemony diminishes.

The future of global governance depends on the ability of the Global South to institutionalize these alternative spaces, transforming the "Geography of Punishment" into a geography of sovereign cooperation. Ultimately, in the 21st century, territorial autonomy is inextricably linked to the construction of a financial and legal architecture that is truly multilateral and immune to unilateral extraterritorial coercion.

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